

Sociology of E-Learning: A Social Observational Trek at Universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone

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Abstract

Social e-learning is acquiring several solid grounds in University enlightenment right through the universe and Sierra Leone not an exception. Recently, a generous amount of universities globally promote social e-learning in divergent shapes. Despite this extensive embracement of social e-learning in university tutelage, sociological inquiry on social e-learning approbation proposes that it has not accomplished its maximum implicit. This sociological inquiry converses the privileges that prevail and demurrers that obstruct the thriving embracement of social e-learning automation as a social norm of tutelage at designated universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone. The sociological verdicts and observations accommodated are anticipated to reinforce universities evolve their social e-learning approaches. The respondents of this inquiry are university lecturers who are commencing to utilize social e-learning. The resultants denote that social e-learning at greater of the universities is still at its conception pulpit. This sociological inquiry unmasks a multitude of considerations or rationales for the restricted attainments, which are associated to architectural growth, advance and didactical reflections for e-learning. Universities are financing further and upgrading organizational operating system at the cost of Erudition Oversight Customs (EOC) operating system that bolsters instruction and education or scholarship. This sociological inquiry proposes that competent advancement or businesslike programs with underscore on e-learning didactics besides the formulation of social e-learning facilitate constructions should be championed.

Keywords: *Sociology of E-learning, Social, Observational, Universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone.*

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Introduction

Cybernetics is incredibly attracting further extensive right through University social education universally. This is harmonious with United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization's 2023 GEM report background papers for Automation in Tertiary Education which compels Graduate Learning establishments to make greater utilization of the merits submitted by the growth of cybernetics to enhance the

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accouterment and standard of their tutelage. Numerous universities across the globe are spinning to the utilization of cybernetics, recent holistically related to as social e-learning, as an adjunct to pedagogue directed tutelage on the citadel of learning (Parvin et al, 2023).

Granting the social e-readiness notify of 2019 disclosed an important drift of focusing funds regarding social e-learning, the similar recounted that the utilization of contemporary automations for education and tutelage in Freetown, Sierra Leone is still at an embryonic podium. Particularly not many establishments of Graduate learning were financing in the pursuit of parallel knowledge cultural communities. A concentration on integrated knowledge and utilizing automation for capability were stated.

Nonetheless, advancements in the utilization of Cybernetics in instruction and education have been bustling at a swift rate in tertiary education in the era of less than two years since that recount was announced, despite not all advancements have been growing. Oversight groundwork has been positioned tailored towards the bolster of the utilization of Cybernetics as an instruction and knowledge device. In rational strive to advance the standard education in Freetown, Sierra Leone universities are rotating to Cybernetics to expand optional transmission modes. Social judgments from the e-learning Readiness Survey (2019) specified the surfacing preferences for social e-learning and instances of social e-learning in Sierra Leone. Numerous universities in Sierra Leone have identified the utilization of social e-learning programs as one of the integral optional transmission social systems for education and practice (USL Cardinal Scheme, 2021; NU Imperative Plan, 2020). It has been recognized that social e-learning has the possibility to metamorphose the social organization and system of instruction and might elevate the social growth of surpassing plausible procedures (Rajah, 2023). It is felt that cybernetics can augment not only the productiveness of the informative progress, likewise its comprehensive competence both in terms of lecture room social engagements and jurisdiction.

Intent of the Inquiry

This sociological inquiry scanned the utilization of social e-learning universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone. Its intent was to furnish a synopsis of the popular station of social e-learning in Universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone. The sociological inquiry identified the range of social e-learning engagements and limitations to its utilization in Sierra Leonean universities.

Social Inquiry Interrogates

The inquiry desired to respond the following social inquiry qualms;

- What social e-learning construction and assets are feasible in universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone?
- What social e-learning engagements were intended in, or are being promised in universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone?
- What are the demurrers encountered by universities as they administer social e-learning in instruction and education?

Literature Evaluation

The term social e-learning has initiated many divergent interpretations or expositions. It was consequently, embodied this sociological inquiry to land at a sentiment in specific Sierra Leonean University regarding what is implied by the term social e-learning and its pragmatic appeal.

The theory of social e-learning is portrayed considerably in literature sources to the stretch that several authors and social e-learning approaches have postulated whether there is demand to espouse a particular interpretation of social e-learning endlessly, considering it may combat probing and limit social heterogeneity. It is, accordingly, significant that individuals have an interpretation that is adequately expansive to consolidate all perspectives of social e-learning, and that is not submitted outdated via the admittance of further contemporary automations.

Social e-learning in its immense sanity can be interpreted as instruction delivered via an automatic communications involving the Cyberspace, service loops, satellite transmission, phonic or video clips, compact disc, relational Tube and Organization network (Shapoval et al, 2021) perceive social e-learning as utilizing cybernetics in instruction and education.

Just recently, laptop dockets for social e-learning entailing of devices such as font, visuals, vids, cubic articles and animation, have been evolved. Parallel lecture rooms can also be utilized to widen education emergency. In order to bound the range of this sociological inquiry, for it to be adequately stuffed, O'Neill's (2023) interpretation is maintained. O'Neill (2023) interprets social e-learning as any shape of social learning that utilizes a laptop or cybernation system for transmission, relation or collaboration.

The foundation of these interpretations of social e-learning are synthesis, execution and affinity of the engagements for education and instruction via divergent digital communications, whether online or offline. The social interpretations referenced above are substantially significant to the range of social e-learning engagements implemented in Freetown, Sierra Leone.

Social Spaces, Education Cultural Community and Student Social Personality

In this segment of this social review, an assessment into instruction and education milieus, student personality and education cultural communities, placing specific stress on the aspects pinpointed by the reviewed literature to be of particular significance for vocational education students knowledge observation in online and mixed programs. Numerous inquiries have identified that the online component of integrated education has significant inferences for students social observation of the knowledge atmosphere (Bangura, 2023), the knowledge cultural community and their self-learner individualism (Lily et al, 2023).

Several inquiries stress the stretch to which the absence of the physical milieu in non-contemporary online instruction mitigates the contingency of direct relation between students and tutors. Although the significance that is still lodged to physical communication in students knowledge observation (Dubey, 2023). Notwithstanding, the similar and other inquiry has directed to the merits that the online instruction community proffers (Apriyanto and Adi, 2021). For instance, in terms of drifting the knowledge community to a further social, elastic and individual social space and consequently enhancing a student centralized mentation and social constructivist strategy to education. The latter is, nonetheless, considerably conforming a trait articulated to portray modern social knowledge cultural communities in holistic.

Based on Almeheyawi (2024), the online knowledge cultural community will not, nevertheless, supplant engagements occurring in physical cultural communities in graduate learning. Reasonably, their inquiry depict that both the physical and web based knowledge cultural communities have their exclusive utilization; but also their restrictions. Consequently, they summarize that both cultural communities job

collectively in appreciative directions for students if an encompassing pattern for mixed knowledge is embraced. Especially in vocational education, privileges for practice attached workplace engagements are significant for student's knowledge observation. Notably, it is the obtainability and docility of workplace social spaces twenty hours parallel or physical that is identified as crucial for students. Further based on this comparative inquiry, the physical synchronous workplace offers a knowledge social space for students bolstering hands on vocational instruction, collaborative learning and automatic guidance, while the parallel contemporaneous workplace emerges to be exceptional suitable for formative dialogue, authentic of scheme advancement and retrospect of personal or partner improvement.

As stated previously, student's observation of the education community and their self - novice personality emerges to be importantly impacted by the online element of mixed social education. Multiple inquiries direct to the contradictions that is essential in the incorporation of cybernetics into the education and instruction observation (Cibu et al, 2023). In other words, it is indicated that online education oversight structures often utilized in online and mixed education establish contemporary chances for reciprocity between student and content, between student and tutor and among students themselves. Conversely, the digital education community proffered by education oversight structures is also one in which student's neighborhood dispersal; non-parallel engagement and restricted visible contact are held for granted. Consequently, the prudence of familiarity to an expressive education cultural community is emphasized as a significant element in online or mixed education student's knowledge observation specifically because it is arduous to make their social sight discernible in the online social community. Nonetheless, inquiries have interacted students consciousness of familiarity to significant online education cultural communities to their engagement and education accomplishment. Notwithstanding, despite perceived as a critical element, student to student relations and cooperation engagements are not imperatively the unique requirement for online or mixed education students to experience part of an education cultural community. The presence of engaging academic content and a robust instruction sight are considered essentially significant for formulating this passion.

Considering the constructing of significant education cultural communities is a distinguish challenge in online or mixed education because of the prejudice or full absence of physical social relation between student and instructors and among students, numerous inquiries have examined how and the expanse to which digital education automations can be utilized to assist students reason of participating of a cultural community of learners.

Intimately connected to the qualms of students rationale of familiarity to a significant education cultural community in online and mixed education communities is the qualms of student's observation of their self-learner personality (Dennen and Arslan, 2022). Based on Tlili (2023), the establishment of learner personality is engrossed in with agency and emotions of being in authority stemming from emotions of familiarity to an education cultural community. They additionally assert that the growth of a robust and imperative online personality plays a significant functional function for student reservation and inducement in online education programs. For that very purpose, their inquiry looks into how successful online education symposiums afford to social and scholarly synthesis as a means of consolidating students learner personalities. Their outcomes divulge that students previous observation with social communications sites such as Facebook tended to be transmitted to the academic

online education forum and consequently to affect both adversely and impressively on their learner assurance and engagement. For example, the communal setting of the online symposium made several students perceive their notifications embrace an atmosphere of jurisdiction and proficiency, which, on the other hand, led other students to abstain from disclosing owing to feelings of lacking education capability. Lastly, absence of nobleman reaction or tutor restrain appeared to be injurious to student's learner personality because they perceived ostracized from and supplementary to the scholarly cultural community of the symposium.

In this section of the discourse, the aspects that have proved most prominent in terms of their significance for education in online and mixed education programs involve the following:

- a) Adequate instruction and education social spaces online as well as off-line;
- b) Engaging and imperative education communities as a means of assisting student's social interactions and their education observation;
- c) A robust and salient consciousness of learner personality.

Trajectory Blueprint

Trajectory blueprint induces student maximization and their perceived education, and multiple factors can contribute to better outcomes in this perspective. An overall contribution may be discovered in the proposition that differentiation in (online) instruction and education engagements are imperative, but the social engagements and propositions for particular trajectory blueprint can be multitudinous when social inquiry is to submit a response.

Mixed education blueprint can prosperously blend online social engagements with application the field and consequently ready future pedagogue instructors for their ensuing job in the vocation. Presently, inclusions of cyber communal devices and job with cyber literacy of the students are or should be fragment of commonplace practice. Hut (2024) focuses on leveraging mixed education for heralding authentic knowledge in instructor education, and summarizes that via conscious trajectory blueprint and the utilization of significant cyber devices, mixed education can render future pedagogue instructors a cyber-podium for collaborative and inquiry lodged education connected to application in the domain. Conversation affairs supplement the cohort job and the instructors are available and functional or sporty throughout the students domain job span.

In vocational education, it is of lofty significance that the online as well as the on campus engagements relate to the vocational existence to come, and as vocation programs have both content and expertise as part of the educational program, trajectory blueprint should consequently be established to assist knowledge transmission and competences acquisition. Davies et al (2023) discover that this could be accelerated by the utilization of cyber automation by students in a flipped lecture room or in a mixed configuration of online and offline social engagements. Additionally in a social inquiry (Hulsbergen et al, 2023) among virtual students, a mixed education blueprint was carved for physical forums, with focus on application analogous engagements, models, portrayals and contemplations, and online symposiums with contemporaneous dialogues, domestic evolved education alternatives and dynamic and available instructors. An innovative facet was discovered in the binary combinations of both online and offline engagements and of concept application engagements.

Multitude consent that it is significant to engage especially future pedagogue instructors in promoting their capacity to utilize appearing automations to promote instruction strategies that assist interactive, engaging and collaborative education, and numerous inquirers (Erdogan and Serefli, 2021) concentrate on the pedagogical merit of dialogue to reinforce future pedagogue instructors ruminative applications and boost their knowledge of the merit of conversation for education. Ke et al (2023) unearth the utilization of multiple social systems in a mixed education environment as a means of integrating further relational discourse via complex devices innovative social models. They summarized by stressing the constructive impact that social dialogue as a didactical instrument had on the students education observations. Notwithstanding, an inquiry by Abdallah et al (2023) prospect the aptitude of student generated webinars as a structure of communal growing social evaluation beyond range. The discoveries depict that the observation empowered the instructor training students to develop the skills and confidence to initiate further autonomous inquiry into automations to assist their didactical intents.

It can, nonetheless, be demanding to establish adequate learner assistance and connect the online social engagements to campus resources (Bye et al 2020) in order, for instance, to avoid students evaluation of online engagements as reduced esteemed than on campus personages. A response to this demand may be discovered in instructors standing of engagements and the relation between them. Several propose that an overarching didactical frame, explicit standing of education engagements (through podcasts or online tutorials), adequate utilization of communications, hands on assessment responsibilities and student-staff communication are pivotal for student's education social observation in a mixed education milieu. Furthermore, it is discovered that instructors might demand to raise online symposium conversations in details in the commencement, establish regulations for them (For example, when, how and how much to notify to the symposium) and contact the non-engaging students. As several students discover that online meetings and instruction is reduced esteemed because of reduced demand in the online engagement, it is significant top spotlight interactive social dialogues, relations and standing of the online engagements. Consequently, there is a demand for numerous directions of assistance to enable several of these future pedagogue instructors to be validated online learners, and a demand for directions in which students can connect meditatively with content.

Likewise, several students discover that peer-to-peer assistance is reduced esteemed, and the impact of peer assessment seems to vary based on students education thresholds; low and average accomplishing students depicted considerably upgraded conduct but reduced impact on the conduct of lofty accomplishing students. Nevertheless, social inquiry often discovers that peer-to-peer education directs to maximization among students in online education cultural communities (Martin and Bolliget, 2022), and that social relation and networked education among peers should be involved in efficient online education, for example, in order to assist self-contemplation and not only to submit entrance to social particulars.

Not only is social relation discovered to establish engaging education in mixed environments, so can online resources when utilized appropriately. In this social path, Eltahir and Ahmed (2023) discover that students appraise cyber lectures to be an added merit, particularly when they function as trajectory devising and as a medium of integrating knowledge and enhancing education across ethnic cohorts and cultural gender. Multiple inquiries also discover that chances for relation between students

and their educators are extremely significant both to their maximization and education upshot.

Modus Operandi

This sociological inquiry ventured to approximate the current threshold of application of e-learning in Sierra Leonean Universities. The inquiry granted the assembling of significant data and information in relation to this contemporary method of instruction and education. The social inquirers reflections are grounded on questionnaire responses from eighty six lecturers, who were randomly selected, as well as social dialogues with Cybernetic administrates from four principal universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone. The representative dispersal is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Dispersal of the Representative of the Sociological Inquiry

Gender	Digit	Allotment
Male	46	66%
Female	24	36%

The questionnaire was fashioned to gather data on their threshold of cyber expertise, their threshold of preparedness to adopt e-learning as well as the challenges they encountered. The questionnaire had both closed and open end questions. The encounter cogency of the questionnaire was constructed by giving the questionnaire to specialists to remark on its cogency.

The questionnaire was supervised in person to 86 university lecturers by the inquirer. Dialogues with cyber directors were reached to elucidate certain issues hoisted in the questionnaire. The upshots are submitted in the adjacent segment.

Results and Discussion

Social E-Learning Infrastructure: Equipment and Package

The information gathered depicts that restricted evolutions have been made in relation to e-learning infrastructure in the universities. The digit of network points contrasted to the digits of consumers at each university depicts that there is a squat cyber consumer quotient. The transmission speed magnitude is excessively diminutive for university demands. A synopsis of the network infrastructure in the four universities is depicted in Table 2.

Table 2. System Infrastructure

System Delivery	University of Sierra Leone	Njala University	Limkokwing University of Technology	Milton Margai University of Science and Technology
Digit of System Spikes	3000	1000	350	4000
Digit of Consumers	12 000	10 000	1 560	6 000
Magnitude Transmission speed	2DPI	1 DPI	2 DPI	2 DPI
Genre of Cyber space Loop	Hired wire	Hired wire Catoptrics	Hired wire	Wireless Loop Dial

Considering access to laptops (Table 3), seventy seven percent of the respondents stipulated that they had access to laptops in their offices. Sixty-nine percent stipulated that they utilized laptops to scheme their lectures. As depicted in Table 3, a reasonable digit of respondents, thirty four percent, stipulated that they had access to laptops for instruction with their students.

Table 3. Academics Access to Laptops

No.	Inquiries	Yes	No
1	Do you own access to a laptop in your office?	66(77%)	20(23%)
2	Do you own access to laptops for instructing your students?	29(34%)	57(66%)

Note: N= 86

Table 4. Utilization of laptops by Academics

No.	Inquiries	Yes	No
3	If, yes do you utilize the laptop for scheming and expanding your lectures?	59(89%)	7(11%)

Note: N= 66

Considering packages, outcomes depict that two universities utilize open source Education Oversight Networks, that is, for the Milton Margai University of Science and Technology (MMUST) and University of Sierra Leone (USL) as their e-learning scaffolds. All the universities were providing students with access to online library facilities such as online catalogues, e-books, data bases, e-journals and e-books. Nonetheless, it was sad to note that when asked whether there was e- learning oversight equipment at the universities, a few lecturers indicated that they were aware there was one (see Table 5). A useful digit of lecturers (42) indicated that they had no idea of the availability of Education Oversight network platforms at their universities (see Table 5).

Table 5. E-learning package

Package	Digit	Allotment
Collaborative eLearning and eWorking Platform (Education Oversight Structure)	9	14%
Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment	5	8%
Blackboard	0	0%
Any other	20	30%
No. Notion	42	64%

The Threshold of E-learning Pragmatic and Engagements

The information gathered revealed that there is restricted utilization of e-learning resources in instruction and education at universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone. As is depicted in Table 6, only twenty six percent of the lecturers revealed that they were utilizing the e-learning oversight package available at their university.

Table 6. E-Learning Engagements

No.	Question	Yes	No
5	If there is an e-learning oversight package, do you utilize the package in your instruction	17(26%)	49(74%)

Note: N= 66

The outcomes of the inquiry depict that the forms of e-learning proffered by universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone are restricted to a slender scope of the e-learning gamut. Social dialogues with cybernetics administrators disclosed that greater e-learning engagements are restricted to management operations, such as, announcement on the web, notification of time tables, semester results. Instruction and education application is restricted to placement of trajectory guidelines, pamphlets, website links at the expense of utilization of relational devices like conversation symposiums, parley rooms and other interactive social engagements. The e-learning engagements carried out reflect its utilization as assistance devise to the customary physical instruction. As depicted in Table 6, only twenty six percent of the lecturers disclosed that they were utilizing the e-learning oversight package accessible at their university.

Academics Readiness

The gathered data depict that the mass of lecturers at universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone have a satisfactory threshold of laptop competency. Thirty-eight percent of the lecturers disclosed that they could perform basic functions and could utilize the laptop independently. A more fifty nine percent of the lecturers disclosed that they were advanced users of laptops and could do a number of tasks with the laptop. Towards the utilization of the Web, the mass of the lecturers that is sixty five percent revealed that they were advanced users who could utilize the Web to exploit for information besides being able to browse and transmit files on to the Web. Of the balance thirty five percent, thirty percent disclosed that they had basic skills required to browse and utilize e-mail autonomously and five percent disclosed that they could not utilize the Web autonomously. The outcomes are depicted in Tables 7.

Table 7. Academics Threshold of Laptop Competence

No.	Question	Novice	Intermediate	Advanced
6	What is your threshold of competence in utilizing laptops?	3(5%)	24(36%)	39(59%)
7	What is your threshold of competence in utilizing the Web?	3(5%)	20(30%)	43(65%)

Note: N= 66

Despite the mass of academics disclosed that they had the basic skills required to utilize laptops as instruction and education assets, a significant digit of them lacked confidence in the utilization of e-learning podiums. As depicted in Table 8, forty seven percent of the lecturers articulated several skepticism on their threshold of readiness to utilize e-learning podiums accessible at their universities. Only thirty percent of the lecturers revealed that were well ready to support students in utilizing the e-learning podiums. Of the balance seventy percent, thirty eight percent revealed that they were not at all ready and thirty two percent were somewhat ready. It is, consequently, not astonishing that almost all the lecturers (ninety four percent) articulated the demand for vocational growth in the utilization of e-learning podiums (see Table 9).

Table 8. Academic's Intimacy with the E-Learning Podium

No.	Interrogate	Not Ready	Somewhat Ready	Very Much Ready
8	How ready do you perceive you are to utilize the e-Learning podium at your university?	16(24%)	31(47%)	19(29%)
9	How ready do you perceive you are to support students in utilizing the eLearning Oversight Package at your university?	25(38%)	21(32%)	20(30%)

Note: N= 66

Table 9. Vocational Growth Demands

No.	Interrogate	Yes	No
10	Do you perceive the demand for vocational growth in the utilization of the e-Learning podium?	62(94%)	4(6%)

Note: N= 66

As depicted in Table 9, the mass of the academics (ninety five percent) expressed the demand for vocational growth in the utilization of e-learning in their job.

Demurrers

Academics disclosed that they are encountering a digit of demurrers in adopting e-learning assets. As depicted in Table 9, the most commonly encountered demurrers are absence of access to laptop workshops with students (seventy seven percent), inadequate training for academics (seventy six percent), troubles with Web gateway (sixty nine percent) and absence of laptop access in the lecturer's offices (fifty one percent). Other important demurrers are: absence of technological assistance (fifty one percent), absence of administrative or initiative at Faculty threshold (fifty two percent) and absence of consciousness concerning directions of integrating the package into instruction (fifty two percent).

Table 10. Demurrers Encountered by Academics

No. 11	Demurrer	Digit (%)
I	Absence of laptop access in lecturer's offices	44(51%)
Ii	Inappropriate practice for lecturers	65(76%)
Iii	Absence of comfort utilizing laptops	16(19%)
Iv	Absence of students concern	5(6%)
V	Absence of lecturers concern	19(22%)
Vi	Troubles with web access	59(69%)
Vii	The package is too intricate to utilize	7(8%)
Viii	Absence of technical assistance or admonition	44(51%)
Ix	Absence of administrative assistance or initiative at faculty threshold	45(52%)
X	Absence of consciousness concerning directions to combine the package into Instruction	43(50%)
Xi	Absence of access to laptop workshop with your lectures	66(77%)

Note: N= 86

Nonetheless, other demurrers indicated involve heavy instruction loads, absence of confidence in e-learning structures by both lecturers and students, outdated and snail pace laptops and absence of didactical assistance.

Discussion

Despite e-learning is demonstrating snail pace in terms of its embracement in universities, it is obvious that all universities perceive that they should be offering it to all their students. Universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone are currently interested in boosting in their instruction and student education via the utilization of e-learning, despite the outcomes of this sociological inquiry depict that this is being done at a snail pace. Despite e-learning has not yet reformed university instruction and education, it has transformed how several commercials are carried out in the universities beside providing simple access to managerial data, an accomplishment that should not be neglected or ignored. E-learning has had some impact on organizational mercies or deliveries such as admittances, enrolment and fee charge. Nonetheless, it is obvious that this is a restricted strategy to the adoption of e-learning, since e-learning is supposed to benefit the student in the instruction and education procedure. This management stress is degrading its academic utilization consequently inducing academics avoid embracing the innovation.

A university cannot prosperously execute e-learning without fitting aspects of its social infrastructure. It turns out, in this sociological inquiry, that only twenty percent of the lecturers have access to laptops together with their students in the lecture room. The laptop student quotient is extremely low at all the universities. Moreover, the deficiency of transmission speed impacts unfavorably on the access to system assets which involve access to online journals, databases and other e-assets to which a university supports. Given the average bandwidth size available to universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone access to these assets is offered inefficient, with the outcome that the investment is not utilized as appropriately as it should.

The crawling initiate of e-learning by lecturers may partially be due to their lack of consciousness of e-learning facilities and their reported lack of readiness. This can be an outcome of poor collaboration of patrons in the universities during the launch and implementation of social e-learning programs. It can also be analyzed by absence of practice as evidenced by the lecturer's expression for the demand for vocational growth. The outcomes indicate that no university in Sierra Leone is presenting practice and continual personnel to bolster their skills, social education and competencies for the preparation of lofty standard e-learning.

Outcomes depict that e-learning is being executed arbitrarily. Despite there is no stable method for smooth discharge of e-learning, innovative approaches present significant directions that can bolster in the establishment of an appropriate e-learning approach. A centralized bureaucracy, or oversight social structure, in Universities is crucial to executing an e-learning program in a coherent, adequate, and appropriate manner. Despite almost all the universities have several form of a central approach for e-learning or are in the procedure of evolving one, there is dearth of counsel for lecturers as to how they could execute the strategies. It is obvious that universities should align their approaches to incorporate e-learning infrastructure. The outcomes of the inquiry depict that the adoption of e-learning programs in Sierra Leonean universities is portrayed by a dearth of organizational dream, stewardship and solid oversight of the multiple adaptable that carve a segment of transformation within this

circumstance. This sociological observation was made by Bangura (2023) who indicated that less than half (forty three point four) of Sierra Leonean colleges and universities have a critical scheme recognizing conventional intents, or implementation preferences for the functional function of cybernetic in instruction and scholarship, which could substantiate unfortunate to prospective triumph of educational institutions. In Freetown, Sierra Leone, despite all the universities strategic plans have room for the adoption of e- learning in their instruction programs, they do not have approach in terms of who is responsible for what during implementation.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The exposures of this sociological inquiry seem to reveal that there is a snail pace of adoption of e-learning by university lecturers. The utilization of e-learning in universities in Freetown, Sierra Leone has not been fully embedded into the University's instruction culture and pragmatic.

If the provision of e-learning is to become a key element of University education, authorities will require submitting a vast program for staff growth and practice. As Observe, academic staff is appointed on the basis of their subject expertise rather than any proficiency in the areas of didactical blueprint and Cybernetics. As has been debated in this inquiry, the introduction of e-learning automations should always be driven by didactical forethoughts, not by the requirements of the automations themselves. Judging the outcomes of this sociological inquiry, it obviously irrelevant to debate for particular laptop competences for lecturers, as a solution to the trouble observed by lecturers in the execution of e-learning in university education. Despite Cybernetic competences are imperative for execution of an e-learning program; the move towards e-learning delivery should put special emphasis on didactical techniques. This calls for a well ready vocational advancement program to be designed to assist lecturers in the efficient execution of e-learning. The vocational growth practice required is one that expedites and certifies that e- learning automation is flourishingly interwoven into the commonplace engagements as well as ensuring that its utilization will be appropriate and efficient.

Vocational evolvement, as construes in this sociological inquiry, is the incentive which permits the evolutionary procedure to move forward lesser tragic. Indeed, if a shift towards online education is to be perceive as strategically significant, then strategies and practices concerning vocational growth have to be an outstanding domain of interest and one that should be coordinated at university dominant oversight thresholds. Given the discipline based requirements of e-learning growth and the demand to deepen these didactical requirements into the specific Faculty's instruction and education engagements, connect staff should be hired to work in each Faculty to expedite the embracement of e-learning. Lecturers should be offered practice and assistance via their Faculties parallel that for Cybernetic competences.

University growth seems to trade best when assisted by a scope of policies. An institutional critical scheme is essential as the first step in the growth of e-learning. To enable the University to manage its e-learning evolvements, it is proposed that an e-learning approach has to be evolved with broad dialogue. The strategic scheme should pursue, among other things, to:

Recognize the university pedagogic domains where e-learning modes could be employed to best effect, and promote utilization of e-learning in these areas;

Establish mechanisms to assist academic staff in utilizing e-learning facilities and devices to best effect in the advancement and delivery of trajectory blueprints;

Ensure that the standard of trajectory delivery is maximized by utilizing a mixed strategy that utilizes the standout of customary and e-learning modes; and recap the forms of assistance required by students, and ensure that these are bestowed in a proper and effective civility.

It is proposed that an e-learning advancement and assistance team involving Cybernetic associates, Faculty or department based staff be established. The e-learning assistance approach should stress the significance of partnership between Faculties and Universities cybernetics department in delivering e-learning social structure and assistance to lecturers and students. Resistance to transformation is consequently probably to be overcome if academic staff is completely included or have complete ownership in the blueprint, growth and execution of these transformations. Academic staff has to have a comprehension of their contemporary functional functions and the outcomes ultimately generated are absolutely deducible.

The e-learning growth and assistance team would have the authority to carve an e-learning approach, which would expedite the:

- Provision of an e-learning infrastructure and a range of e-learning devices that have lofty standard specifications;
- Cooperation among faculties and departments in the provision of information, training and assistance needed by lecturers and students in the utilization of e-learning devices and expedites;
- Establishment and utilization of efficient qualities and specifications in e-learning growth, involving congruence with availability directions and qualities; and,
- Provision of assistance to lecturers in their evaluations of e-learning growths and where appropriate achieve such assessments, especially at institutional threshold.
- Formulate collaboration with other universities and outsource expertise.

It is further proposed that affiliations and networks be established across the universities as a possible path forward for the growth and diffusion of e-learning in university education in Freetown, Sierra Leone. Affiliation and network building are significant for permitting access to contemporary education, to learn from others social observation and transaction of information about the current growths or advancements in e-learning. Such affiliations can also offer a path for sharing material, joint automation and package advancement, joint sociological inquiry and growth, dual practice and affinity among other stuffs.

References

Abdallah, A., Ismail, O., Abdallah, R. & Alkaabi, A. (2023). Perceptions of Students About the Use of Webinars in Classrooms: A Case of Abu Dhabi University. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education*, 19, 1-17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4018/IJICTE.322793>

Almeheyawi, R., Alsini, A., Aljadrawi, B., Alshehri, L., Algethami, R., Althobaiti, R., Alrubeai, A., Alzahrani, H., Alshehri, F., & Alshehre, Y. (2024). Impact of online learning on physical activity during COVID-19 lockdown period among female undergraduate students in Saudi Arabia: a cross-sectional study. *PeerJ*, 12, e16579.

<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.16579>

Apriyanto, R. & Adi, S. (2021) Effectiveness of Online Learning and Physical education During Pandemic Covid 19. *Kinestiek Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Jasmani*, 5(1), 64 -70. <https://doi.org/10.33369/jk.v5i1.14264>

Bangura, M. (2023) Sociology and Contemporary Education Social Observation in Cultural Fabric and Garment Oversight in Makeni, Bombali District, Northern Sierra Leone. *British Journal of Contemporary Education*, 3(2), 103-123. <https://doi.org/10.52589/BJCE-8ZNOHCMT>

Cibu, B et al (2023) Mapping the Evolution of Cybernetics: A Bibliometric Perspective. *Computers*, 12(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers12110237>

Dennen, P. V. & Arslan, O. (2022) The Visual Performance of Online Identity: Instructor Presence and Personal Across Tools and Settings. *Studies in Technologies*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21428/8c225f6e.9e975efc>

Davies, P., Alotaishan, R., Alabdulwahed, H., Khan, F., Ateya, R., Alkhamis, T. & Alodhieb, A. (2023). Perspectives on cyberlearning: A case study by students, about students. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11564-w>

Dubey, P., Pradhan, R., & Sahu, K.K. (2023). Underlying factors of student engagement to E-learning. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-09-2022-0058>

Eltahir, M.E. & Ahmed, O.S. (2023). Cybersecurity Awareness in African Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study of Sudan. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18576/ISL/120113>

Erdoğan, E. & Şerefli, B. (2021). Use of Technology in Social Studies Teaching: The Journey of Five Teachers. *Journal of Qualitative Research in Education*, 232-256. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14689/enad.27.11>

Hulsberg, M.H et al (2022) Exploring the Use of Online Simulations in Teaching Dialogue Skills. *Psychology and Learning and Teaching*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/14757257221138936>

Hut, K (2024) Cyber Security Domains: A Brief Overview. Retrieved from <https://www.knowledgehut.com/blog/security/cyber-security-domains>

Ke, L et al (2023) Exploring System Dynamics of Complex Societal Issues Through Socio-Scientific Models. *STEM Education*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1219224>

Lily, A. (2023). *Community in Online Higher Education: Challenges and Opportunities*. Centre for Advancement of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning, Avondale College of Higher Education, Cooranbong NSW, Australia.

Martin, H. & Bolliget, D.U. (2022). Developing and Online Learner Satisfaction Framework in Higher Education through a Systematic Review of Research. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19(50). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00355-5>

O'Neill, A. (2023). Was humpty dumpty right? Towards a functional definition of e-learning. *Education and Information Technologies*. 29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11900-8>

Rajah, A. (2023). Cybernetic-Based Instruction: An Innovative Learning Model in the Digital Age. *Qeios*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32388/1Z4U56>

Tlili, A., Sun, T., Denden, M., Kinshuk, Graf, S., Fei, C., & Wang, H. (2023). Impact of personality traits on learners' navigational behavior patterns in an online course: a lag sequential analysis approach. *Frontiers in psychology, 14*, 1071985. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1071985>

Shapoval, O., Kotlyaria, S., Medvedieva, A., Lishafai, O., Barabash, O., & Oleksyuk, O. (2021). Education in Cyberspace: University as Universality. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security, 21*(11), 333–337. <https://doi.org/10.22937/IJCSNS.2021.21.11.45>

UNESCO (2023) Technology in Education GEM Report. Retrieved from <https://www.unesco.org/gem-report/en>

